

Management Information System in the Educational Process

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Abstract: Education is a process involving the following: teaching, training, acculturation, indoctrination, knowledge transfer, discipline, instruction, skill acquisition, command, guide, nurture, as well as change, and lifelong experiences. Eze Rock (2012) remarked on this basis that education is a multifaceted, structured process that results in character transformation or behavioural modification. Similarly, Nnachi (2015) said that for education to have accomplished its goals, learning must occur, and for learning to have occurred, the kid must demonstrate a reasonably long-lasting, permanent change in behaviour. Effective education policymaking in Nigeria involves knowledge on the system's inputs, resources, governance, operations, and results. A management information system for education (EMIS) provides systematic, high-quality data in a structured environment, allowing the information produced to be utilised in planning and policy dialogue. Education Management Information Systems aims to help countries improve data collection, data and system management, and data use in decision-making, thereby enhancing various elements of the education system and contributing to the ultimate objective of enhancing learning for all children and youth. Dike (2017). (2017).

INTRODUCTION

Management information system in education (MISE), also known as education management information system (EMIS), provides education stakeholders with information on the status of the education system as a whole and the learning outcomes within a nation, state, or neighbourhood. By using an EMIS, governments may study and use data to enhance their education systems. Effectively implemented, an EMIS may also assist administration and planning by principals and administrators, as well as classroom instruction and learning. Several value-added components, such as quality data, efficient expenditures, institutionalised data systems, better management practises, data-driven policies, smart investments, and targeted teaching zoikoczy, are generated by an EMIS to increase educational quality (1981). The implementation of management information systems in the educational sector is the topic of this research (MIS). Therefore, it is necessary to underline that MIS is a subsystem of information systems. It must be made clear that the primary objective of EMIS is the collection, preservation, and transmission of data (information) to facilitate sound decision-making in the educational sector.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Management

The components of a management information system are people, machines, procedures, databases, and data models. According to Zoikoczy (1981), the system collects data from both internal and external sources of an educational institution. Management information system is an abbreviation of three words: management, information, and system To fully comprehend the term MIS, let's try to comprehend these three terms (Mass, 1982).

People often refer to management as "the art of getting things done through and alongside groups of other people who are officially organised." Planning as an administrative responsibility Administration of strategy (top management) management control (middle management) control of operations (including personnel and direction) (bottom management). Okunamiri (2010) defined management as the scientific or systematic use of an organization's available human and material resources to achieve its predetermined goals and objectives. To manage is to achieve success with the socio-economic resources available.

In an educational institution such as Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Rumuolumeni, management may refer to the ability of institutional managers to utilise all available natural (Arable-land, trees, rivers and streams, soil, sun, rain, etc.) and human resources (staff, students, preachers, the ruling government, non-academic staff, host community leaders and inhabitants, etc.) to achieve optimal development, academic excellence, and competent institutional goal attainment. In light of this, Mandah (2016) views educational institution administrators and school principals as managers who must be technologically equipped to manage competently and objectively. He also viewed the school as an organisation, the faculty as managers, and the students as consumers, with the information or lesson content serving as the commodity.

INFORMATION

Information is a fundamental resource in our society. Information is "data that has been organized and presented in a meaningful form" (Buckland, 1991, p. 4). Information is also "data that has been given meaning through interpretation and/or evaluation" (Foster, 2004, p. 6). It is a way of organizing and presenting data that can be used to make decisions, solve problems, and understand complex topics.

Information is produced, disseminated, and used by individuals, organizations, and societies. In the modern world, information is generated and shared in a variety of formats, such as books, newspapers, magazines, television, film, radio, internet, and social media. The widespread availability of information has revolutionized the way people live and work, and has created new opportunities for individuals to access and use information. The production, dissemination, and use of information is an important part of the economy. Information is used to support business decisions, generate new ideas and products, and provide consumers with the information they need to make informed decisions. Information can also be used to influence public opinion and shape public policy.

In addition, information is used to create and maintain relationships, both personal and professional. The proliferation of information has also created a wide range of ethical and legal issues. For example, the unauthorized use of copyrighted material can lead to legal action, while the unauthorized dissemination of personal information can lead to privacy concerns. In addition, misinformation can lead to a loss of trust in public institutions and can create economic and social instability. Information is a valuable resource and has the potential to be used for great good or great harm. It is important to think critically about how information is produced, disseminated, and used. It is also important to ensure that information is accurate and ethical.

INFORMATION SYSTEM

An information system (IS) is a combination of hardware, software, and telecommunications networks that people build to collect, create, and distribute useful data, typically in an organizational context (Chen, 2020). It is a collection of tools and methods used to gather, store, process, analyze, and distribute information (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993). IS is used by organizations to support their operations, communication, and decision-making. It helps to manage the organizational activities and make them more efficient (Chen, 2020). ISs are used to store, analyze, and organize data. They also help to track customers, manage inventory, and generate reports. ISs can also be used to automate business processes and create new services. They are used to monitor and analyze customer behavior, allowing companies to make better decisions about their product and service offerings (Chen, 2020). ISs are also used to provide

feedback to customers and employees. For example, customer relationship management (CRM) systems are used to manage customer interactions and provide feedback to customers (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993). ISs have become increasingly important in the modern economy, due to the amount of data being generated and stored.

Organizations are using ISs to manage their data and make better decisions. ISs are also used to create new services and products, as well as to monitor customer behavior. ISs are also becoming increasingly important in healthcare, as they are used to manage patient data and improve patient care (Chen, 2020). ISs have become increasingly complex in recent years, as the amount of data being collected and analyzed has grown. Organizations must ensure that their ISs are secure, reliable, and capable of handling the large amounts of data they are collecting (Henderson & Venkatraman, 1993). They must also ensure that their ISs are interoperable, so they can share data with other organizations. ISs must also be updated regularly to keep up with new technologies and trends. In conclusion, information systems are essential for organizations to manage their data and make better decisions. ISs are used to store, analyze, and organize data, as well as to automate business processes and create new services. They are also used to monitor and analyze customer behavior, allowing companies to make better decisions about their product and service offerings. ISs must be secure, reliable, and interoperable, and they must be updated regularly to keep up with new technologies and trends.

EDUCATION

People who work as educationists or curriculum developers have defined education differently. Education, according to Hornby (2000), is the process of teaching and instructing young people and children in schools and colleges in order to impart information and build skills. Education is a systematised process that facilitates learning or the acquisition of information. Education is a collection of experiences designed to socialise the young person. Education is the process of teaching and learning that enables young people or learners to gain the necessary skills, expertise, knowledge, proficiencies, and bravery to contribute to their community. Kanno (1997). (1997). Formal, casual, or semi-formal education may exist. The purpose of education, according to Nnachi (2015), must be to ensure learning via effective instruction. According to Mandah (2016), education is like a broad canopy that encompasses teaching, information, instruction, and communication. Additionally, he believes that a well-designed educational system must be divided into smaller and simpler units that may be autonomous from the central unit but must function interdependently with other sub-units to accomplish the defined (organisational) objective. In this instance, the ideal objective of education must be character formation or behaviour modification. Without a well-designed information and communication network, education cannot fulfil its objectives; consequently, the education system should be structured similarly to other companies in terms of MIS.

INFORMATION MANAGEMENT

Information management is the organization-wide capacity of producing, keeping, retrieving, and making instantly accessible the correct information, in the right location, at the right time, in the hands of the appropriate people, at the lowest cost, and in the best medium, for use in decision making (Langemo, 1980). In a similar vein, Best (1988) defines information management as the economical, efficient, and effective coordination of the creation, control, storage, retrieval, and distribution of information from external and internal sources in order to enhance the performance of the organisation. This definition is limited in scope since it does not address the management of the properties of the information itself (content, ownership, representation, and equality), regardless of the store medium, processing equipment, or system that utilizes it.

In conclusion, the most important aspect of information management is managing information inside an organization utilizing contemporary information technology.

MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS (MIS) AS A CONCEPT: Developing MIS is one method through which firms might leverage their computer capacity. There is no universally accepted definition of MIS, and the definitions that do exist reflect the authors' priorities and possibly biases.

However, the term "management information system" can also refer to a database management system that is tailored to the needs of managers or organisational decision-makers. MIS is a system that uses formalised procedures to provide management at all levels and in all functions with appropriate data from both internal and external sources, so they can make timely and effective decisions for planning, directing, and controlling the activities for which they are responsible (Argyris, 1991).

It is clear from the preceding definition that the emphasis is on the information's applications. Essential components of "management" include planning, directing, and controlling. The essential function of MIS is the transformation of data into information and the communication of that information to the user. It should be noted that MIS exist in organisations to assist them in achieving their objectives, planning and controlling their processes and operations, dealing with uncertainty, and adapting to or initiating change. The question then becomes: what management functions are facilitated by MIS, and at what decision levels can management information be utilised? It is only through a comprehensive response to this question that the significance of MIS in management can be understood. Mangal and Mangal (2009).

Characteristics of MIS

David (1982) and Stone Cash (1981) observed a functional MIS to be able to play the following characters: **1. Systems Approach:** The information system employs a systems-based methodology. A systems approach entails taking a detailed look at the interdependent subsystems operating inside an organisation. **2. Management Oriented:** The management-oriented quality of MIS denotes that management actively leads system development activities. For MIS planning, a top-down methodology should be used. The top-down method proposes that system development begins with the identification of management's requirements and overarching corporate goals. To guarantee that the execution of the system's policies meets the system's requirements, the management must continuously monitor and participate in the process.

3. Need Based: The design of a management information system should take into account the information requirements of managers at various levels.

4. Exception Based: MIS should also be exception-based, which implies that in the event of an anomalous scenario, the decision-makers at the necessary level should get quick notification.

5. Future Oriented: MIS shouldn't just provide information about the past or history; rather, it should provide information that's based on future estimates about the activities that need to be taken.

6. Integrated: Integration is important because it can result in information that is more useful after it has been analysed. When we talk about integration, we are referring to the process of taking a holistic perspective or looking at the big picture of the interdependent subsystems that are in place inside the organisation.

7. Common Data Flow: Avoiding duplication of efforts, integrating functions that are functionally equivalent, and simplifying procedures whenever it is feasible are all components of common data flow. The idea of creating a common data flow is not only economically viable but also logical; yet, it is essential that this idea be considered from a practical standpoint.

8. Long Term Planning: The development of MIS takes a significant amount of time. There should be a significant amount of time spent planning.

9. Sub System Concept: The management information system (MIS) should be seen as a single entity; yet, it needs to be segmented into more manageable and meaningful subsystems.

10. Central database: In the MIS, there ought to be a centralised data repository for the entire system.

COMPONENTS /RESOURCES OF INFORMATION SYSTEM.

An information system is dependent on the resources of people, hardware, software, data, and networks in order to accomplish the activities of input, processing, output, storage, and control that convert data resources into information. These actions turn data into information. According to Elliss (1986) and Langemo's observations, IS is made up of a number of significant components and resources (1980).

People resources: People are the necessary component that must be present in order for any information system to function properly. This people resource includes: **People** who use an information system or the information that it provides are known as end users, but they are sometimes referred to as users or customers. **They might be clients, salespeople, engineers, or other professionals.** Most of us are **IS** end users. **Information System specialists:** are individuals responsible for the creation and operation of information systems. They consist of individuals responsible for system analysis, the development of software, the operation of systems, and various managerial, technical, and clerical IS positions. **Hardware resources:** It encompasses all of the tangible tools and components that are utilised in the processing of information. The following are some examples of hardware that can be found in computer-based information systems:

Computer system; It is comprised of a central processing unit (CPU) that houses microprocessors as well as a range of peripheral devices that are linked to one another. For example, handheld, portable, midrange, mainframe, and big mainframe computer systems. **Computer peripherals;** which equipment that allow users to enter data and instructions, such as a keyboard or electronic mouse; devices that allow users to output information, such as a video screen or printer; and devices that store data resources, such as magnetic or optical discs.

Software resources: It contains all of the information processing instructions in their entirety. It is not limited to the collection of directives for the system that are known as programmes. Examples are: Software that manages and supports the functions of a computer system, such as an operating system programme, is referred to as system software. **Application software;** which are programmes that guide processing for a specific usage of computers by end users, they are also known as application applications. For example, a software that analyses student enrollments, a programme that calculates compensation for delays (both academic and non-academic), and a word processing system. **Data resources:** Databases that carry processed and structured data are one kind of data resource that is often managed, stored, and accessed by a number of technologies that are categorised under data resource management and fall within the purview of information systems. Langemo is referring to knowledge bases, which store information in a number of formats including facts, rules, and cases (1980).

Network resources: technologies and networks for the transmission of communications, such as the internet, intranets, and extranets. The idea that communications technologies and networks are basic resource components of all information systems is emphasised by the notion of network resources. Network resources consist of the following: **Communications media:** This covers wireless technologies such as microwave, cellular, and satellite networks, as well as twisted pairs wire, coaxial cables, and fibre optic cables. **Network infrastructure:** This broad category highlights the fact that a wide variety of data technologies—including hardware, software, and data—are required to enable the functioning of communication networks and the usage of such networks.

FUNCTIONS OF MIS IN EDUCATION

Objectives of MIS especially in the field of teaching and learning according to Achuonye (2004) include:

1. Data Capturing: The management information system collects data from a wide variety of internal and external sources inside the organisation that is the school. The collection of data may either be done manually or via the use of computer terminals. The following types of

information are going to be collected: purchases made by the schools, admissions, student enrollment, nominal rolls for instructors and lecturers, staff wages, and so on.

2. Processing of Data: The information that is necessary is created by processing the data that has been gathered. Calculating, sorting, categorising, and summarising are all examples of operations that are included in the processing of data, which is an essential component to the efficient operation of any educational institution.

3. Storage of Information: The data, whether processed or not, is saved for further use in the MIS system. Any information that is not immediately needed is put into a record for the organisation and stored for later use if it is not immediately necessary. These may contain things like the findings of the student's evaluation, copies of the student's claimed certifications, and an accumulation of the student's academic records for the purpose of creating transcripts.

4. Retrieval of Information: The different professors, students, or members of the school administration may request that MIS extract information from its many repositories, and it will do so (users). A good illustration of this would be the situation in which students' payment data, bank statements, receipts, and academic scores go missing as a consequence of theft, a fire breakout, or misplacement; the MIS is the only system that can recover such sensitive information.

5. Dissemination of Information: Users inside the company get the information that is produced as a final byproduct of MIS. This process is known as "dissemination." It may be done online using a computer terminal or on a periodic basis. This is something that can be observed in areas such as the online release of student results, admission lists, payment requirements, matriculation and convocation dates and events.

ROLE OF MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

There are a number of ways in which the role of the management information system (MIS) in an organisation and the function of the heart in the body may be compared and contrasted. The information functions as the body's blood, and MIS performs the role of the body's heart. In order for all of the tissues and organs in the body, including the brain, to be able to perform their jobs, it is necessary to have oxygen-rich blood pumped through the body by the heart, which is the function of the heart. When there is a need for more blood, the heart beats at a faster rate and pumps more blood than normal. It processes the impure blood that is being taken, performs regulation and control over the blood while it is being drawn, and then delivers the processed blood to the destination in the quantity that is necessary. It meets the needs of the blood supply of the human body during both ordinary operations and times of emergency, allowing it to be used in either situation.

(1) The system ensures that relevant data is acquired from a variety of sources, analysed, and then sent further to all of the required destinations. According to Belle and co. (2001), who say that the MIS performs the exact same function inside the organisation, this is the conclusion that may be drawn.

(2) It is expected that the system would fulfil the information needs of an individual, a group of individuals, and the management functionaries, which include the managers and the top management. This is the case since it is designed to do so.

(3) The Management Information System (MIS) is outfitted with a diverse collection of systems, such as Query Systems, Analysis Systems, Modeling Systems, and Decision Support Systems, which enables it to fulfil a broad spectrum of needs. In order to assist with Strategic Planning, Management Control, Operational Control, and Transaction Processing, the Management Information System is helpful.

(4) During the processing of transactions, the MIS offers assistance to the clerical workers and responds to their questions about the data associated with the transaction, the status of a particular record, and references on a variety of documents. Additionally, the MIS provides

references on a variety of documents. By providing the junior management staff with the operational data necessary for planning, scheduling, and control, the management information system (MIS) is able to be of assistance. In addition to this, the MIS provides assistance to the personnel in question when it comes to making choices at the operational level in order to rectify a situation that has spiralled out of control.

(5) Middle management receives aid from the management information system in the areas of planning, goal formulation, and the regulation of the operations of the organisation. This is accomplished via the use of the management tools of planning and control, which offer the organisation with assistance. The Management Information System offers support to top management in the areas of goal formulation, strategic planning, the development of business strategies, and the implementation of those plans.

(6) The MIS is accountable for the generation of information, the conveyance of that information, the identification of issues, and the support that it gives in the process of decision making. As a consequence of this, the management information system, often known as MIS, plays a very significant role in the management, administration, and operations of the school as a whole.

(7) The business function is one of the most extensively utilised basis for arranging activities in practically every educational institution. This is proven in the works of Adedewoyin,(2002) and Adeyanju (2000).

REQUIREMENTS OF MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEM IN EDUCATION.

The following are the four primary resources included in the information system:**hardware, software, people and data.** The following are the four primary resources included in the information system:**Software:** includes all set of information processing instructions. **People:**All information systems cannot be successfully run without the participation of individuals (Best, 1988).

These human resources include specialists and end users; teachers, students as well as non teaching staff. **Data:**is the foundation upon which information systems are built. Managers and information system experts have been instrumental in expanding our understanding of the ideas of data resources.

Likewise, the implementation of management information systems in the educational sector requires having enough coverage in eight major areas of responsibility, as stated by Dike (2017). This is a requirement for the implementation of management information systems. These aspects include data management, computing and data management architecture, information systems development, information technology acquisition, training, and technical support. Planning information systems, organisational structures, and personnel are all included in this category.

CHALLENGES OF MANAGEMENY INFORMATION SYSTEM IN EDUCATION

Knowledge and information are foundational building blocks for every effective educational institution. Despite this, a great number of nations suffer with problems that are intertwined, such as inadequate regulations and an architecture for their data systems that is lacking in strength. According to Ciotea (2004), these obstacles prevent data from being properly utilised to monitor and improve education results and have disturbing consequences for the overall aims of international education. For the following reasons, there is an urgent need for a tool that can evaluate an existing EMIS in a nation or decide whether or not the government needs to develop a new system:

Countries are unable to make decisions about education policy based on statistics because of the absence of certain data. Important data is often unavailable, and even when it is, it may be difficult to make effective use of it. The main tool for systematically monitoring progress toward and encouraging responsibility for the achievement of these objectives should be a country-level

EMIS. In other nations, there is either no information system at all, or the indicators connected to educational objectives are not being recorded in a methodical manner.

In the context of Nigeria, Mandah (2016) made the insightful observation that a significant obstacle in the field of EMIS is the negative attitude that some Nigerians have toward the dissemination of information and innovation. In addition, he regarded the unreliable supply of electric power as a technological cancer that was plaguing the information and communications technology era.

According to Nowduril and Dosary (2012), these problems are widespread, which makes it difficult for governments and the international community to keep track of the progress being made toward the goal of making education accessible to everyone.

Other challenges accrued to use of MIS include the following:

- 1) A lack of engagement from management in the design of the management information system;
- 2) An unsuitable or too narrow focus of the computer system; and
- 3) An excessive focus on low-level data processing applications, notably in the accounting sector.
- 4) A lack of understanding on the part of information experts about the genuine information needs of management and the issues facing the organisation; and
- 5) A lack of support from upper management.

CRITERIA FOR EFFECTIVE EDUCATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

The EMIS tool analyses policy intentions as well as the degree to which policies are actually successfully implemented in the field. The term "intent" is used to describe the manner in which decision-makers explain an EMIS and its overall goal, and then codify that intent in laws and regulations, as well as in standards and strategy papers. Simply evaluating someone's intentions does not provide the whole picture. As a result of this, the EMIS evaluation also examines the implementation of policies. The term "implementation" refers to the extent to which the goals of a policy are realised in the day-to-day operations of stakeholders operating at all levels of the education system. According to Dike (2017) and Nnachi (2015), the following are the requirements for efficient education management information systems, which are based on substantial study and evidence from across the world:

Enabling Environment: The institutionalised procedures, human resources, infrastructure capacity, and budget of the system make up the enabling environment. The legal framework and organisational structure of the system are also included in this environment. This encompasses not just the legislation but also the policies that surround an EMIS. In its most basic form, this policy area serves as the setting for the operation of an EMIS.

System soundness. The procedures and structures of the EMIS should be able to provide support for the components of an integrated system in a reliable way. As a result, data pertaining to education are obtained from a variety of institutions, and each and every one of these data contribute to and constitute the EMIS. The databases that are included inside an EMIS should not be regarded as independent databases but rather as an integral component of the EMIS. Important facets of the robustness of the system include the types of data that are included in EMIS and the manner in which these data are integrated into the larger system.

Quality data. When gathering information, storing it, creating it, and using it, all of these procedures should assure accuracy, security, and the production of high-quality, timely, and trustworthy data that can be used in decision-making. The quality of the data is a multi-faceted term that involves more than simply the underlying correctness of the statistics that are provided.

It indicates that the data is not only accurate but also responds to certain requirements in a timely manner.

Utilization for decision-making. It is necessary to employ an EMIS across the whole of the education system in order to arrive at choices that will allow for the implementation of initiatives that will enhance educational quality. The development of more well-informed plans and programmes is made possible by the collection of precise data on the performance of the education sector. It is of the utmost importance to identify the location of decision-making, whether or not the ability to analyse and interpret educational data exists, and whether or not particular data is accessible to guide decision-making. Obrien and Marakas (2007).

IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATION MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS

Contributing to the enhancement of educational systems: When evaluating the state of education in a nation, it is necessary to have information about the inputs, resources, governance, operations, and outcomes of that nation's educational system. This information must be reliable, pertinent, and easy to access. Alipoor,(2013).

In a variety of different ways, including the ones listed below, MISE gets education policymakers and stakeholders closer to this degree of system knowledge and insight. providing a methodology to evaluate a MISR through the critical policy areas; assisting countries in analysing their educational systems through diagnosis, dialogue, and reform; providing a comprehensive framework that is based on a thorough review of global evidence that presents international best practises in MISE. providing a methodology to evaluate a MISR through the critical policy areas. Enhancing the level of knowledge possessed by people all across the globe by putting into effect effective MISE policies Including key members of the system's leadership as well as relevant stakeholders in the process of defining change goals, Argyris, (1991). (1991).

According to Patterson (2005), the relevance of management information systems also includes the following: addressing global issues, maximising organisational effectiveness, and maximising profitability. Taking advantage of available chances in the industry, In accordance with the company strategy, Bringing together departments that perform a variety of duties, Increasing the efficiency of the workforce An improvement in the overall quality of products and services.

In point of fact, a management information system (MIS) is a specialised computer system that is helpful for management inside a company. The Management Information System (MIS) functions as a readily available and swiftly moving conveyor belt for relevant and high-quality information from its point of creation to its consumers. Therefore, the central component of an efficient MIS is a database that has been meticulously thought of, planned, and implemented. Its level is equivalent to adaptive choices, as described by David (1982) and Stone Cash (1981).

The introduction of management information systems (MIS) has eventually resulted in an increase in the amount of essential management information. The increasing popularity of management information systems (MIS) has resulted in a significant amount of effort being put into the creation of methodologies and software for the management of data. It is essential to stress, however, that the focus of the most recent iteration of management information systems (MIS) is not on the processing of the information, but rather on the uses to which it is put. This aspect of the system has been given a great deal of importance. According to Shim (2000), management should "get things done via people" through making use of information pertinent to the situation that is obtained from MIS. According to Kempner (1976), the performance of an organization's resources inside the organisation is a significant factor in determining the efficiency of the company's overall performance. Information is essential to the operation of all facets of management in the present day. It is a common belief that knowledge equals power, and that whomever has it is in a position of authority. However, nothing can progress in the absence of information.

MANUAL VERSUS COMPUTER BASED MIS

The manual based MIS: It is entirely reliant on the efficacy and capabilities of the various human and non-scientific activities in terms of the collection, storage, and dissemination of information. It does duties such as hand writing, paper and pen computations, utilising human agents or medium in sending or delivering written letters and other critical missives, and it uses human agents or medium to execute such jobs. Best (1988). (1988).

A Manual (Informal) Information System is an employee-based system that is designed to meet both personal and vocational needs, as well as to assist in the resolution of work-related issues. In addition to this, it relays information to higher-ups via more covert means. It functions properly within the parameters of the company and the regulations that it has outlined. It interacts with educational policies and the curriculum in the various educational institutions. According to Mass (1982), manual MIS does not necessarily require machines, mobile phones, computers, or electronic media for the purpose of information processing. In a manual-based MIS, the authors Adedewoyin (2002) and Adeyanju (2000) found that paper file jackets, manual typewriters, manual (paper) libraries, handwritten letters and other correspondences, and storing files in shelves and rackets were the most common types of hardware. In addition to that, it required and still requires putting certain sensitive files that contain life-essential information in a location known as "the strong room."

Patterson (2005) made the observation that some of the many drawbacks of manual-based MIS include the following: the information could be lost at any time due to the fact that it was all saved as hardware materials; such information is lost in the event of a fire or flooding; thieves and criminals can have easy access to the offices where the files are stored; the information could be lost at any time. No one else will be able to relocate the information in the event that the person who possesses the file is involved in an accident or dies. According to Salton (1975), any time a human being who possessed certain information became ill or passed away, that information was considered to have died at the same time. When compared to the amount of data that can be stored on a relatively small flash disc, the number of documents and other types of information that can be stored in an office is laughable to think about. The process of manually marking and recording the examination scores of all of IAUE's undergraduate students would be far too time-consuming and laborious to be practical.

However, based on what we've seen, manual MIS may be utilised in some situations to save costs. This is especially true in regions where the persons in charge of the offices do not have enough computer literacy; hence, the manual method might be used to store the information in these situations.

Computer Based Information System (CBIS): We are used to hearing the word "CBT-TEST," which stands for "Computer based test." This is a common example of a computer-based information system. As students in Nigeria, we are used to hearing this term. When it comes to the management of business applications, this kind of information system is almost entirely dependent on computers. System analysis is the process of developing a variety of information systems to fulfil a wide range of business requirements. Kempner (1976) made the observation that there is a category of systems that is collectively referred to as computer-based information systems. They may be divided into the six categories that are as follows: i) Transaction Processing System (TPS), ii) Management Information System (MIS), iii) Decision Support System (DSS), iv) Executive Support System (ESS), v) Office Automation Systems (OASs), and vi) Business Expert Systems (BESs) and computers, iii) Decision Support System (DSS), iv) Executive Support System (ESS), v) Office Automation Systems (OASs), and vi) Business Expert Systems (BESs), and computers Eze Rock (2012). The present period of management information systems is known as computer-based MIS, and it is characterised by the predominance of ICT and computers.

Information management systems are a subset of computer information systems that are designed to gather and handle data coming from a variety of diverse sources in order to facilitate

managerial decision-making at all levels. Information management systems for businesses To assist in the formulation of sound business decisions, information should be made available in the form of reports and presentations that have been predetermined. The next level in the organisational hierarchy is filled by low level managers and supervisors, and it is the level that comes after that. This level is home to various computer systems that are designed to provide operational management with assistance in monitoring and exercising control over the transaction processing operations that take place at the clerical level. The information that is gathered by the TPS is used by management information systems, or MIS, to generate the appropriate control reports for supervisors. According to Dike (2017), a management information system is a sort of information system that takes internal data from the system and summarises it into relevant and usable forms as management reports. This information may then be used to assist management operations and decision making.

CONCLUSION/ RECOMMENDATIONS

In the course of this research, efforts have been made to investigate the Management Information System in Education, as well as its challenges and significance in the context of an organisation. One might reach the conclusion that MIS is the central nervous system of any company. Before making any judgements, the public and private sectors must demonstrate a commitment to gathering information in a formal or structured setting.

The use of computer simulations and gaming strategies will allow for the provision of customised solutions to management issues. The managers of today need to exercise caution because they run the risk of becoming irrelevant if they are merely furnished with data that are just slightly relevant rather than being given knowledge that is solid and totally valuable. This predicament may be averted by putting in place a MIS unit that is robust and capable of performing its functions. In an educational setting, the school is viewed as an organisation whose data, including that pertaining to students, non-teaching staff, all academic records, and extracurricular activities, must be adequately recorded, kept, and disseminated when it is required to do so. This includes information regarding teachers, land and buildings, students, and non-teaching staff.

Therefore, it is the recommendation of the authors of this paper that all schools should adopt the computer-based Management Information System for a more competent academic outcome and to be in line with the world's best educational practises with regard to ICT. This recommendation was made because the authors of this paper believe that the adoption of such a system will allow schools to be more in line with current education trends.

REFERENCES

1. Achuonye, K.A. (2004) *Contemporary Educational Technology*, Portharcourt, Pearl Publishers.
2. Adedewoyin, J.A. (2002) *Introduction to educational Technology*. Lagos: Johns and Lad publishers LTD.
3. Adeyanju, J.L. (2000). *Basic Concepts in Educational Technology*. Ile-Ife, Oluwa Publishing Co.
4. Alipoor, H. (2013). Role of Management Information Systems (MIS) in Decision-Making and Problems of its Implementation, *Universal Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, Vol. 3, No.3, pp. 78–89.
5. Argyris, C. (1991), “Management information systems: the challenge to rationality and emotionality”, *Management Science*, p. 291.
6. Belle, J-P.V., and Eccles, M.G., and Nash, J.M. (2001) *Discovering Information Systems*.
7. Best, D.P. (1988), “The future of information management”, *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 8 No. 1, March, pp. 13-24.

8. Buckland, M. K. (1991). Information as thing. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science*, 42(5), 351-360. doi:10.1002/(SICI)1097-4571(199105)42:5<351::AID-ASIA>3.0.CO;2-7
9. Chen, Y. (2020). *Information Systems: Fundamentals, Concepts, and Applications*. Oxford University Press.
10. Ciortea ,M. (2004). Aspects Regarding The Types of Process Control Systems, *International Conference on Theory and Applications of Mathematics and Informatics*, pp.90–95.
11. Daniel, E. (1982), “1980s forecast: special librarian to information manager”, *Special Libraries*, Vol. 73 No. 2, pp. 64-72.
12. Dike, H. I. (2017), *a modern textbook of educational technology with chapters on digital audio-visuals and online learning*, port Harcourt, copic publishers.
13. Duff, W.M. and Asad, M.C. (1980), *Information Management: An Executive Approach*, Oxford University Press, London, p. 243.
14. Ellis, D. (1986), “Information management and information work”, *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 15-26.
15. Eze Rock. (2014) *Educational Technology; theory and practice*, Okigwe, landline publishers.
16. Foster, N. (2004). A concept of information. In D. C. Westerlund (Ed.), *Information and Knowledge Management* (pp. 1-13). Hershey, PA: Idea Group.
17. Henderson, J. C., & Venkatraman, N. (1993). Strategic alignment: Leveraging information technology for transforming organizations. *IBM systems journal*, 32(1), 4–16.
18. Hornby, A. S. (2000) *Oxford advanced learners dictionary*. New York, oxford university press.
19. Horton, F.W., Hasan, Y., Shamsuddin, A., and Aziati ,N. (2013), The Impact of Management Information. In Kempner, T. (1976), *Handbook of Management*, Penguin, Harmondsworth, p. 216.
20. Khanore ,S., and Patil ,R., and Dand,H. (2011) *management information system*, Institute of Distance and Open Learning , University of Mumbai.
21. Langemo, M. (1980), “Records management/word processing – a needed team effort”, *Records Management Quarterly*, Vol. 14 No. 4, pp. 10-14.
22. Laudon, K. and Laudon, J. (2006) *Management Information Systems: Managing the Digital Firm*, 9th ed. Prentice Hall.
23. Mandah, N. N. S. (2016) *Issues in educational Technology*, Portharcourt, EmmanestVeentures Publications.
24. Mangal, S. K. and Mangal, U. (2009) *Essentials of Educational Technology*: Newdelhi, phi learning private limited.
25. Marrchard, D. (Eds), *Information Management in Public Administration*, Information Resources Press, Arlington, VA, pp. 170-84. Heidarkhani, A., & khomami ,A.A, & Jahanbazi ,Q., and Co.
26. Mass, R. (1982), “Records, words, data ... whatever you call, it’s still information – Part 1”, *Information and Records Management*, Vol. 16 No. 6, pp. 18-20.
27. Nowduri1, S., and Al-Dossary ,S. (2012). Management Information Systems and Its Support to Sustainable Small and Medium Enterprises *International Journal of Business and Management*; Vol. 7, No. 19, pp. 125–131.
28. O’Brien, J.A., & Marakas, G.M. (2007) *Management information systems -10th ed.*, by

McGraw-Hill/Irwin, a buunit of The McGraw-Hill Companies.

29. Okunamiri (2010), *educational administration; theory and practice*, Abia, ABSU publications
30. Patterson, A. (2005) *Information Systems - Using Information, Learning and Teaching* Scotland.
31. Salton, G. (1975), *Dynamic Information and Library Processing*, Prentice-Hall International, London, p. 523.
32. Shim ,J.K. (2000) *Information Systems and Technology for the Non-information Systems Executive*, by CRC Press LLC.
33. Stonecash, J.C. (1981), “The IRM showdown”, *Infosystem*, Vol. 28 No. 10, pp. 42-8.
34. Zoikoczy, P. (1981), *Information Technology: An Introduction*, Pitman, London, p. 157.